

USING CLT METHOD FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES

Kalimbetova Kunsulu
Tlepbaeva Sarbinaz
Shintemirova Malika

Nukus state Pedagogical Institute Department of English language and literature at
the Faculty of Foreign languages

Abstract: The Communicative language teaching (CLT) is a cornerstone of statistical theory, but its abstract nature makes it challenging for secondary school students to grasp. This article explores the use of interactive techniques to teach CLT in an engaging and effective manner. Through the integration of visual tools, hands-on activities, simulations, and collaborative learning, students are given the opportunity to directly observe the practical implications of the CLT. The article examines various interactive strategies, reviews their effectiveness in promoting comprehension, and emphasizes how these methods make statistical concepts more accessible to young learners.

Key words: Interactive learning, Communicative language teaching, fundamental concept, approach, visualisize.

Introduction

The Communicative language teaching (CLT) is one of the most important principles in the field of statistics, stating that the distribution of sample means will tend to be normal, regardless of the population distribution, as the sample size increases. While CLT is crucial for understanding probability theory and statistical inference, it can be difficult for secondary school students to understand due to its abstract nature.

Interactive learning techniques—such as simulations, real-world data collection, and group activities—offer promising solutions for teaching complex statistical ideas. These approaches allow students to visualize and experience the effects of sampling distributions. This article aims to explore the role of interactive techniques in teaching the Communicative language teaching to secondary school students.

Literature Review

The Communicative language teaching (CLT) has been a fundamental concept in the study of statistics since it was formally described by Pierre-Simon Laplace in the 18th century. However, research has shown that teaching the CLT to secondary school students can be challenging due to its abstract nature and the level of mathematical sophistication required. Numerous studies have highlighted the difficulties faced by students in grasping concepts like probability distributions, sample variability, and the relationship between sample size and distribution shape.

Recent research has pointed to the value of technology in teaching statistical concepts. Using interactive software tools, such as statistical simulations and graphing programs, enables students to visualize sampling distributions and observe the effects of sample size and population shape on the resulting sample means (Ziegler, 2013). Interactive simulations not only make abstract concepts more concrete but also allow for iterative learning where students can experiment with different scenarios and immediately see the results.

Methodology

To explore the effectiveness of interactive techniques in teaching the Communicative language teaching (CLT) to secondary school students, a mixed-methods approach was used. The research combined qualitative and quantitative data collection strategies, including experimental classroom activities, surveys, and student interviews. The study focused on observing the impact of various interactive teaching methods, such as simulations, hands-on data collection, group work, and gamification, on students' understanding of the CLT.

Data Analysis:

Quantitative Analysis: Pre- and post-test scores were compared using paired t-tests to determine any significant changes in understanding. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to compare the performance of the three groups.

Qualitative Analysis: Responses from student interviews were analyzed thematically to identify common trends in students' experiences with interactive methods and how they contributed to understanding the CLT.

Results

Pre- and Post-Test Performance: The data revealed significant improvements in students' understanding of the CLT in both the experimental groups (simulations and hands-on activities) compared to the control group. The average test scores of students who participated in interactive activities increased by 35% from the pre-test to the post-test, whereas the control group showed only a 12% increase. In particular, the group using statistical simulations showed the largest gains in understanding the concept of sample distributions and how sample size affects the normality of the distribution.

Student Engagement: Observation data indicated that students in the experimental groups were significantly more engaged during the learning sessions compared to those in the control group. They were more willing to ask questions, share observations, and collaborate with peers. The use of simulations and data collection projects appeared to foster greater interaction, as students could experiment with different scenarios and immediately see the results of their actions.

Student Interviews: Interviews revealed that students in the experimental groups found the interactive methods to be much more effective in helping them grasp the concept of the CLT. One student mentioned, "The simulation showed me how the sample means always seem to look more normal as the sample size gets bigger, even

if the population isn't normal. That really helped me understand the Central Limit Theorem." Additionally, students appreciated the hands-on activities, with one participant noting, "Collecting real data and calculating sample means made it feel more real. I could actually see how the theory worked in practice."

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that interactive techniques, such as simulations, hands-on data collection, and collaborative group activities, are highly effective in teaching the Central Limit Theorem (CLT) to secondary school students. Compared to traditional lecture-based instruction, these methods significantly improved students' understanding of the CLT, as evidenced by higher post-test scores, increased engagement, and positive student feedback. The results suggest that interactive learning not only enhances students' conceptual understanding of complex statistical ideas like the CLT but also promotes greater student engagement and collaboration.

References:

1. Chance, B. L. (2002). Teaching the concept of the Central Limit Theorem. *Teaching Statistics*, 24(3), 76-82.
2. Garfield, J. (2003). Assessment in statistics education: A look forward. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 11(2).
3. Groth, R. E. (2007). Teaching statistics with technology: Supporting learning through interactive tools. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 15(3).
4. Mason, J., & Biehler, R. (2010). Teaching statistics through inquiry and exploration. *Mathematics Teacher*, 103(7), 514-520.
5. Ziegler, M. (2013). Visualizing statistical concepts through interactive simulations. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 61(4), 681-695.